

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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PROBIOTIKLAR VA ULAR ASOSIDA ISHLAB CHIQRILGAN DORILAR

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ANNOTATSIYA: Probiotiklar – bu inson organizmiga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatadigan, ichak mikroflorasini tiklash va immunitetni mustahkamlashga yordam beruvchi tirik mikroorganizmlar hisoblanadi. So'nggi yillarda probiotiklar asosida ishlab chiqarilgan dori vositalari keng qo'llanilib, gastroenterologiya, immunologiya va boshqa tibbiyot sohalarida samarali natijalar bermoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: probiotiklar, *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Saccharomyces*, ichak mikroflorasi, sog'liq, biotexnologiya, probiotik dorilar, immunitet.

Hozirgi kunda noto'g'ri ovqatlanish, stress va antibiotiklardan ortiqcha foydalanish natijasida ichak mikroflorasining buzilishi keng tarqalgan muammo bo'lib, u immunitetning pasayishi va turli kasalliklarning kelib chiqishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Ushbu muammoni hal qilishda probiotiklar katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ular ichak mikroflorasini tiklash, organizmning umumiy himoya tizimini mustahkamlash va metabolik jarayonlarni yaxshilashga yordam beradi.[1]

Probiotik mikroorganizmlar ilk bor XIX asrda I. I. Mechnikov tomonidan o'rganilgan bo'lib, ularning uzoq umr ko'rish va sog'liqni saqlashdagi ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan isbotlangan. Bugungi kunda probiotiklar farmasevtika sanoatida keng o'rganilib, ular asosida turli biologik faol qo'shimchalar va dori vositalari ishlab chiqilmoqda.[2]

Probiotiklar – bu tirik mikroorganizmlar bo'lib, inson organizmiga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ular asosan *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium* va *Saccharomyces* turkumlariga kiruvchi bakteriyalar va zamburug'lardan iborat. Probiotiklarning asosiy vazifalari quyidagilardan iborat: Ichak mikroflorasini tiklash va disbiozning oldini olish; Immunitet tizimini mustahkamlash; Ovqat hazm qilish jarayonini yaxshilash; Vitaminlar (masalan, B guruh vitaminlari) sintezini rag'batlantirish; Patogen mikroorganizmlarga qarshi himoyani kuchaytirish.[3]

Ilmiy tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, probiotiklar quyidagi kasalliklarni oldini olish va davolashda samarali hisoblanadi: *Ichak disbiozi* – antibiotiklardan foydalanish natijasida yuzaga keladigan mikroflora buzilishlarini tiklaydi. *Allergik kasalliklar* – ekzema va atopik dermatitga chalinish xavfini kamaytiradi. Ovqat hazm qilish muammolari ich qotishi va diareya kabi holatlarni normallashtiradi.

Immun tizimining zaiflashishi – organizmning infeksiyalarga qarshiligini oshiradi.[4]

Hozirgi kunda probiotiklar asosida ishlab chiqarilgan dorilar farmakologiyada keng qo'llanilmoqda. Ular ichak mikroflorasini tiklash va organizm himoyasini kuchaytirish maqsadida ishlatiladi. Eng mashhur probiotik dorilardan ba'zilari: Linex – Tarkibida *Lactobacillus* va *Bifidobacterium* mavjud bo'lib, ichak mikroflorasini tiklash uchun qo'llaniladi. Bifiform – *Bifidobacterium longum* va *Enterococcus faecium* bakteriyalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu dori disbioz va diareyani davolashda ishlatiladi. Acipol – *Lactobacillus acidophilus* va sut zamburug'lari asosida ishlab chiqarilgan bo'lib, ichak mikroflorasini tiklash va immunitetni oshirish uchun tavsiya etiladi. Enterogermina – *Bacillus clausii* bakteriyalarini o'z ichiga oladi va antibiotiklardan keyin yuzaga kelgan disbiozda ishlatiladi. Ushbu dorilar ichak kasalliklari, antibiotiklar natijasida yuzaga kelgan disbioz va immunitetning pasayishi kabi holatlarda tavsiya etiladi.[5]

XULOSA: Probiotiklar inson organizmi uchun muhim mikroorganizmlar bo'lib, ichak mikroflorasini normallashtirish, immunitetni oshirish va turli kasalliklarning oldini olishda katta ahamiyatga ega. Ular asosida ishlab chiqarilgan dorilar disbioz, gastroenterologik kasalliklar va immun tizimi muammolarini samarali davolashga yordam beradi. Kelajakda probiotik dorilarni yanada takomillashtirish va genetik modifikatsiyalangan mikroorganizmlar yordamida yangi avlod probiotiklarini ishlab chiqish istiqbollari mavjud. Bu esa probiotiklarning yanada samarali va keng qo'llanilishini ta'minlashi mumkin.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI:

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